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NAVIGATING GLOBAL MARKETS: THE CRUCIAL ROLE OF LEADERSHIP IN BUSINESS TEAM PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT:

Objective: This study aimed to investigate leadership's role in enhancing business teams' performance. The research question focused on identifying common skills among business leaders that distinguish them and exploring how these skills impact sales teams.

Methods: Employing a deductive approach, the study sought to uncover the essential skills requisite for success among leaders in the business domain. Recognizing the imperative for organizational adaptation amidst escalating globalization, emphasis was placed on delineating leadership competencies crucial for navigating competitive market landscapes.

Results: The findings underscored the pivotal role of managerial leadership in driving organizational effectiveness, particularly in facilitating improvements within the studied company. Identifying avenues for enhancement emphasizes the potential of bolstering leadership efficacy and consequent bottom-line benefits.

Conclusion: Enhancing leadership skills within the business context holds promise for augmenting team performance and overall organizational success. As businesses navigate evolving global dynamics, the centrality of effective leadership in fostering competitiveness

becomes increasingly apparent, positioning leaders as critical drivers of strategic advancement and sustained growth.

KEYWORDS: Leadership; Commercial; Business; Teamwork.

INTRODUCTION:

Teamwork is a good strategy for any business because a cohesive, well-managed, and motivated group of workers can devise creative and effective ways to serve the business's marketplace, always looking for new ways to meet customer needs. When organizations encourage teamwork and look for new ideas, they can get better results. This is because people working together get better and faster answers (Hekneby & Olsen, 2024; Khan, Latif, Shahid, & Shah, 2024).

When teams work well in a business, they solve problems, are more creative, and are more engaged. Some people think that collaboration happens when people get together to talk about work. Some people also say it happens when people don't argue, fight, or bother each other and when everyone gets along. It's also thought to occur when a community makes choices through voting, a form of democracy. People who work in sales and marketing for a company need to know their exact role and be responsible for making sure that the actions are carried out successfully (Cole, Narayanan, & Vickery, 2024; González-Mohíno, Donate, Guadamillas, & Cabeza-Ramírez, 2024).

After all, individuals get things done, so they need to know how important they are and what they can do to help the cell work. Most of the time, businesses want to get good results, go above and beyond their goals, and become effective in today's challenging global market. Because of this, some companies offer good pay and other perks to keep their employees motivated. However, this isn't always enough because many businesses don't have enough ways to grow, even if they spend a lot of money on them (Aghimien, Aghimien, Aigbavboa, & Dhladhla, 2024; Gilli, Lettner, & Guettel, 2024).

Every day, there are significant changes in organizations. In a market where competition is fierce and businesses do anything to stay ahead, teamwork is essential for the growth of the organization and the individuals working in it. In other words, businesses and groups have used the make-up of work groups to get things done over the years. Organizations must work together efficiently and as a single unit, committing to quality and taking responsibility for completing

tasks with a purpose. In other words, managers must try to track their teams' performance to find any problems and help them do better (Kallio, 2024; Xu & Wang, 2024).

For this research, an organization from Monte Azul Paulista, SP, was asked to send a survey to its sales team. This team works with marketplaces, grocery stores, suppliers, bakeries, grocery stores, bars, and restaurants in the area to sell food items from different brands. There are 11 people on the sales team: a sales boss and ten salespeople. The goal is to use a questionnaire to determine how the salespeople's boss motivates them to make sales (Fabisch, Kjellström, Ockander, & Avby, 2024).

In this situation, and because leadership is essential in the business and sales areas of companies, this study is appropriate, as it is thought that understanding the traits and duties of leadership is critical to the success of sales teams. Therefore, the main goal of this study is to find out what skills leaders in the business side of a company need to have (Tseng, Jade, Weng, & Lu, 2024).

TEAMWORK: CONCEPTS AND PRINCIPLES

Companies need people to reach their goals and objectives, so getting these people to work together towards a shared goal is one of the hardest things for managers to do. For this reason, putting together skilled, motivated, and well-aligned teamwork can be among the primary ways a company stands out. Now that the world is more connected, businesses have become more focused on teamwork to make money, and their structures are more united. Organizations work together to keep their members because they always try to stay relevant in the market. Having inspired and united teams can be a company's biggest differentiator (Talib Aljaradi, Navajas-Romero, & Muñoz-Benito; Tao, Wang, Robson, & Hughes, 2024).

Luz says that working together as a team is suitable for both people and businesses:

Teams can help organizations break down traditional barriers between departments and improve the functional structure by making it easier for people to talk to each other, coordinating and integrating tasks better, and, most importantly, requiring faster response times. Teams are a robust way for people to work together informally within organizations. Teams make people more socially and emotionally involved, which leads to more commitment and, in turn, more drive (Prudjinski, Hadar, & Luria, 2024).

It is imperative to learn how to tell if the workers you're considering put teamwork first and know how to value unions, unity, and relationships getting along with each other. Maxwell says each person serves a purpose and relies on others for the best performance possible. One person does most work tasks at a time, but "teamwork" means putting in much effort (Chen, Chen, Kang, & Zhou, 2024).

You must know how to improve group skills like dedication, cooperation, discipline, morals, habits, persistence, and the capacity to get things done at work. These days, most businesses agree that working with others is helpful. This is because teams are better at their jobs in some scenarios. After all, they have a more comprehensive range of skills, opinions, and experiences. The team comprises a few people whose skills support each other. They all work together towards clear goals and are responsible for each other (Mitchell, Gu, & Boyle, 2024a; Robiah, Telaumbanua, Marzuki, Zulkipli, & Dwiputra, 2024).

To put it another way, a team has to agree to do the suggested work or project. As you can see, a team comprises people working together to reach a shared goal. Teams can be formal, with clear roles and responsibilities, or informal, where they form naturally at work. Chiavenato says that teams are over just groups of people because they have traits that groups don't have, as illustrated in Table 1 (Sun, Zuo, Huang, & Wen, 2024).

GROUPS	TEAM
They are groups of people without a common objective	They are collections of people with a common goal in mind.
People make individual decisions.	People make decisions together.
No interconnectivity or exchange of ideas	They have strong interconnectivity and exchange of ideas.
The result from the sum of people's efforts	They result in a multiplication of people's efforts
No emotional or affective interaction	People act collectively
People may have the same interests.	There is a strong emotional or emotional interaction.
People act individually	People have and share the same interests.

Table 1: Difference between group and team

Table 1 shows the difference between a team and a group.

Some companies care about teamwork because they know that when people work together, they can get things done faster, better, and for less money. There is no winner or loser in teamwork; everyone either wins or loses. It's like a football, volleyball, or basketball team: everyone knows their part but plays as a whole. It is also important to remember that trust between team members is essential for a pleasant environment where communication can quickly happen. When people work together, dealing with personalities that don't get along is much more complex. When some people complicate things by being annoying, insecure, or even competitive, the group loses unity, and things get tough (Garrido, 2024; Y. Zhang & Li, 2024).

HIGH PERFORMANCE TEAMS:

According to their needs, leadership is the service that involves influencing people's behavior and promoting successful outcomes in the organizations where they work. It means knowing how to motivate, integrate, and act in a wide range of situations and having the power to control. Leadership plays a central role in interpersonal interactions and ensures the dedication and performance of each person. When you think of leadership, words like boss, general, chief, manager, and leader come to mind (Febrieani & Subagio, 2024; Scheiterle, Martellucci, & Dal Mas, 2024).

Regardless of this, it is noted that the following is how the idea of leadership is presented: "Giving people access to diverse perspectives, circumstances for their interests, and methods of observation, thinking, and being is what constitutes leadership, rather than imparting knowledge and skills." dedication and productivity. Given the significance of the idea, it implies that charisma, expertise, flexibility, understanding, and the ability to solve issues from all angles should be used to lead rather than force (Shang, Kuo, Hsu, Lai, & Ye, 2024).

People are compelled to act against their will when power is employed because of their position. However, they will act by their own free will when they employ persuasion. In all human institutions, leadership is crucial and imperative in organizations. Leadership doesn't happen inside individuals; instead, it occurs in the framework of relationships and coordinating behaviors within a community.

It should be mentioned that being a leader is not a prerequisite for influencing how well work groups perform; rather, different leaders can inspire teams to become dedicated, successful teams or teams that diligently carry out their duties and goals to achieve a particular outcome but fall short of meeting expectations (Kilag, 2024; Yun & Beehr, 2024).

The ability to influence others is always a prerequisite for leadership; a leader must act to convince his team members of their decisions and demonstrate his dedication to each one. Offering people something they haven't accomplished for themselves is a critical component of effective leadership. The goal of what the manager does is to create an environment where workers feel more empowered to take initiative on their own. Along with commitment to the group, sensitivity, and collective intuition, leadership is also essential (Sjahrudin, Sari, & Hakiki, 2024).

The leader needs to be a people manager first and foremost. As such, he must follow through on his statements and set a good example for those under his supervision. Winning over people closest to you is what it means to be a leader. When you establish a close relationship with him, be aware that this is more common in certain presumptive attitudes than it is in actuality. These attitudes are noteworthy and have been stuck in our leaders' memories for a long time (Dewi, Nugraha, & Dafrosa, 2024).

EXCELLENT PERFORMANCE UNITS:

According to Duarte, performance refers to the abilities and qualitative traits of a person, piece of machinery, or organization's output. Working as a team can produce excellent results, according to Maxwell. This is because teamwork and unity have a positive and multiplicative effect, which benefits everyone involved by improving individual skills. Once more, Maxwell states that "their teammates always esteem and respect the team member who can take them to the next level, someone who helps them develop and allows them to succeed." Put another way, a sacrifice is made when functioning as a team; the most successful team members constantly put the group's success above their own (Nguyen, 2024; Orozco Collazos & Botero, 2024).

To put it another way, Levintin states that fire is typically put out by a team and the fire brigade commander; in other words, managers play a crucial role, but task execution also requires the individuals who carry things out. The efficiency of a team's collaborative process

becomes apparent quickly because better, more noticeable, and faster results are achieved when more team members grasp the productivity concepts and methods.

Hill was organizing a working group that produced a set of rules for teams (Widelska, de la Morena, & Barba, 2024).

These recommendations include advice on creating a community, such as accepting accountability for the group's accomplishments, removing obstacles, establishing an all-leader group, speaking out, acting honestly and listening intently, and restraining oneself from trying to alter or fix others. These rules can be summed up as follows: commitment to coworkers; behavior that entails realizing one's barriers and learning to set them aside to voice dissatisfaction to the group; communication that requires assertiveness, speaking in the first person, speaking profoundly and personally; and ending listening communication that aims to listen intently to colleagues; avoid parallel conversations; refrain from interrupting; and resist the urge to "fill the gap" with your speech (Chamberlin, Nahrgang, Sessions, & de Jong, 2024; Sheng, Peng, & Jiang, 2024).

METHODOLOGY:

In light of this, this work will create a bibliographic analysis of the significance and function of the leader in the business world and in a company's sales process, as perceived by experts. The work's technique was specified, and the Deductive method was selected. As explained by Nardi and Santos, this approach guarantees that the conclusion is founded on one or more premises and always leads to a decision. As defined by Nardi and Santos, the descriptive character of the research is characterized by the empirical research being conducted to summarise or evaluate the features of facts or events (Aumentado, Balagtas, Cu, & Teng-Calleja, 2024).

The problem will be approached using quantitative research, which, in the words of Longaray and Beurun, takes the stance that all things can be quantified. This entails turning ideas and data into numerical forms to categorize and evaluate them. It needs statistical tools and methods, such as regression analysis, percentage terms, mean, mode, median, variance, standard deviation, and correlation factor. To gather information, a survey was created and distributed to ten sales representatives from a particular company that operates in the Monte Azul Paulista, SP, metropolitan area (Yavuz Aksakal & Ulucan, 2024).

Concerning the questionnaire, questions about the sales leadership's function in leading and inspiring the studied sales team were created and distributed to the ten sales representatives included in the sample. After the questions were ready, the online questionnaire was distributed to the merchants. About the application's submission period, the investigation was conducted between April 22, 2020, and April 26, 2020 (XIAOPING & ALI, 2024).

RESULTS:

This chapter presents the findings from an applied research study conducted in a food company, where ten sales representatives were recruited from the company's sales staff. The survey was administered from April 22, 2020, to April 26, 2020. The research findings will be shown below (Aroussi, Saeed, Harguem, & Chabani, 2024).

1) Does your leader have a commercial background?	Answers	%
No	2	20%
Yes	8	80%
I don't know how to respond	0	0%
TOTAL	10	100%

Table 1: Training for leaders

According to Table 1's results, 80% of respondents stated that their manager has a history in business, while 20% said they did not. It is acknowledged that training in the role in which the leader is assigned is crucial since he will offer the guidance and expertise required for his group to produce optimal outcomes (S. Zhang, Mo, & Liu, 2024).

2) Does your leader know the commercial area, perform tasks well, guide the team, and achieve goals and objectives?	Answers	%
You have good knowledge	2	20%
You know, but not enough	1	10%
No knowledge about this aspect.	0	0%
You have excellent knowledge	7	70%
TOTAL	10	100%

Table 2: Expertise in the business domain

About the skills and knowledge of the leader, 70% of respondents stated that their leader possesses excellent knowledge, 20% said that their leader has decent knowledge, and 10% indicated that their leader is knowledgeable but not enough. A finding suggests that most of the leaders in the study group know the inquiries. Mutual trust is necessary for teamwork to succeed and foster a cordial communication environment. Dealing with diverse personalities in a team setting is much more challenging when certain group members continue inflaming the atmosphere with their trivialities, fears, or rivalry. This leads to a breakdown in group unity and makes things extremely challenging (Mitchell, Gu, & Boyle, 2024b; Porter, Amber, & Stoverink, 2024).

3) Which of the following traits does your leader NOT have?	Answers	%
Good task performance	3	30%
Ability to direct the team	2	20%
Commercial area knowledge	1	10%

Reach goals and objectives	1	10%
None	3	30%
Total	10	100%

Table 3: Information lacking by the leader

When asked what qualities the respondents' leader lacked, 30% of respondents said their leader lacked the qualities mentioned. Still, another 30% said their leader performed tasks poorly, 20% said he could not lead the team and accomplish goals and objectives, and 10% said their leaders lacked business management expertise (Davai & Gunkel, 2024).

4) Please select the three primary skills that stand out in your leader below:	Answers	%
Building teams	4	13%
Leadership	6	20%
Team communication	0	0%
Team motivation	7	23%
Influence on team	3	10%
Decision making	3	10%
Trading	4	13%
Political and cultural consciousness	0	0%
Conflict Management	0	0%

Confidence	3	10%
TOTAL	30	100%

Table 4: Key competencies of your leader

Since the question allowed for numerous responses, the research's findings revealed that, when it comes to the qualities that set a leader apart, 23% of the people surveyed said that their leader's ability to inspire team members is their strongest suit, followed by 14%. Who stated that the team makes the difference? 13% said that negotiating stands out, and 10% said that trust, decision-making, and impact on the team stand out (Santarpia, Sommovigo, Brecciaroli, Consiglio, & Borgogni, 2024).

5) Does your leader seek to motivate the team to pursue results?	Answers	%
Yes, always motivating	8	80%
I don't feel motivated in the team	0	0%
Yes, sometimes it does motivate	2	20%
It never motivates	0	0%
TOTAL	10	100%

Table 5: The team's leader inspires them to pursue goals

Regarding team leader motivation, the findings indicate that 80% of participants believe their leader stimulates them constantly, with 20% stating that this happens occasionally. These findings demonstrate that the project managers of the studied company inspire their team, which probably benefits the organization and promotes the accomplishment of the project's goals (Shanks, Scott, Mende, van Doorn, & Grewal, 2024).

6) What role does the leader play in motivating sales?	Answers	%
Notably, he also motivates the team.	1	10%
It is imperative; without it, you have no motivation	9	90%
Unimportant, the team is self-motivated by the project goals and objectives	0	0%
TOTAL	10	100%

Table 6: The Leader's Function in Advancing Sales

In response to a question concerning the leader's significance in inspiring projects, 90% of respondents stated that it is crucial and that there would be no inspiration without the leader and 10% said that it is significant and inspires the team. These results are displayed in graph 6 (Kamara, Bangura, Bangura, & Koroma, 2024).

These days, each group has a manager, coordinator, or leader whose job is to bring about results by bringing together the efforts of several people. He is giving them direction by exerting control. Every member is aware of their individual and group roles, responsibilities, and tasks. According to Hunter, being a leader motivates others to work passionately towards objectives that advance the common good. Regarding interpersonal interaction, control, and decision-making, the relationship between leaders and their subordinates is far more intricate than the explanations of their daily routines and procedures they claim to outline. A more comprehensive understanding of how the leader's role can affect the team's performance was made possible by the study's findings (Zheng, Hu, Wu, & Bai, 2024).

As previously indicated, the goal was to gain a deeper understanding of the actions and tactics employed by the team leader and how these affect the outcome. Each response leads us to

the conclusion that having a knowledgeable leader is crucial to creating a successful team. We observe certain exchanges among the leader; therefore, her subordinate is absent, and the team in the organization where the survey was used is not entirely motivated (Wang, Yao, & Gao, 2024).

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS:

In the business world, the management or leader greatly aids a project team's ability to accomplish its goals. Throughout the production, its role is evident. However, to find the qualities that make a leader in a company's commercial area stand out, a survey was conducted. Ten questionnaires were submitted, and the results revealed that 80% of the respondents said their leader had training in the business sector, while 20% said they did not.

Participants acknowledged that their managers have excellent knowledge, as demonstrated by the study's emphasis on leader abilities and expertise. Not as startlingly, some respondents claimed that 30% of leaders perform subpar work. Regarding extraordinary leadership qualities, the study revealed that 23% of participants said their leader's strength motivates the team.

Regarding leader motivation inside teams, the findings indicate that 80% of respondents believe their leaders motivate them consistently. In this way, it is acknowledged that the study's goal has been met and that the findings offer some changes regarding the commercial leader of the study's company's function, which requires improvement to boost the team's sales performance.

To conduct a comparison analysis, it is advised that future work create a program to enhance communication among leaders and their followers in projects implemented in other organizations with multiple personnel.

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